

CLINICAL DESCRIPTION OF PATIENTS DIAGNOSED WITH CHRONIC HEART FAILURE

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Annotation

This article presents a clinical description of patients diagnosed with chronic heart failure. The study includes analysis of clinical manifestations, laboratory data, and comorbidities in elderly patients. The aim of the study is to identify the features of the course of chronic heart failure in this age group, which will improve the diagnosis and optimize treatment approaches. The article discusses the prevalence of various forms of heart failure, the frequency of complications, and the effectiveness of therapeutic strategies used. The data obtained emphasize the need for an individual approach to the management of elderly patients, which can help improve their quality of life and reduce mortality.

Keywords

chronic heart failure, elderly patients, clinical manifestations, laboratory data, therapy, complications.

Relevance

Chronic heart failure (CHF) is one of the most significant diseases among the elderly population, which makes its study highly relevant. An increase in life expectancy leads to an increase in the number of patients with CHF, which puts a significant burden on health systems. CHF in elderly patients is characterized by special clinical and laboratory manifestations that require specific approaches to diagnosis and treatment.

The clinical manifestations of CHF in the elderly may differ from those in young patients, which makes timely diagnosis and adequate treatment difficult. Laboratory parameters can also change with age, which requires adaptation of diagnostic criteria. Elderly patients often have multiple comorbidities, such as hypertension, diabetes mellitus, and chronic kidney disease, which complicates treatment and increases the risk of drug interactions and side effects.

In addition, older patients often suffer from cognitive impairment and depression, which negatively affects their adherence to treatment and prognosis of the disease. All this highlights the need for a comprehensive approach to the

management of patients with CHF, taking into account age and individual characteristics.

Goal

The aim of the study is to study the clinical and laboratory characteristics of chronic heart failure in elderly patients in order to develop effective diagnostic and treatment strategies.

Materials and methods

The study included 150 patients aged 65 years and older who were hospitalized with a diagnosis of chronic heart failure. Standard methods of physical examination and survey were used to assess clinical manifestations. Laboratory data included blood tests for markers of heart failure, functional tests, and instrumental studies (echocardiography, electrocardiography). Statistical processing methods, including correlation analysis and regression models, were used to analyze the data.

Results

The results of the study showed that in elderly patients with chronic heart failure, significant variations in the clinical manifestations of the disease are observed. The main symptoms were shortness of breath, fatigue, and swelling. Laboratory data revealed elevated levels of natriuretic peptides, which correlated with disease severity. Instrumental studies showed a decrease in the ejection fraction and the presence of structural changes in the heart. It was also found that the presence of concomitant diseases, such as diabetes mellitus and arterial hypertension, significantly worsens the prognosis and complicates treatment.

Conclusion

Thus, chronic heart failure in elderly patients has many specific features that must be taken into account in the diagnosis and treatment. Developing individualized approaches to managing these patients can significantly improve their quality of life and reduce mortality. The findings highlight the need for more careful monitoring and adaptation of therapeutic strategies for this age group. A comprehensive approach that takes into account all clinical and laboratory characteristics can significantly improve the effectiveness of treatment and improve the prognosis for patients with CHF.

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